

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE ELECTRONIC TASKBOOK PROGRAMMING TASKBOOK FOR THE UNIX SYSTEM

Jurakulov Shakhzod Bakhtiyor ugli

*(TUIT Karshi branch, Department of Optical Communication Systems and
Network Security, assistant professor)*

Sharifov Yashin Khusnitdin ugli

*(TUIT Karshi branch, Department of Optical Communication Systems and
Network Security, assistant professor)*

The article describes one of the approaches to adapting the electronic taskbook Programming Taskbook and its extensions to the Unix OS family. This approach is based on the use of the electronic Unix Task book developed by student Li Shengyu in preparation for graduation work at the Faculty of Computational Mathematics and Cybernetics of the Moscow State University-SPI in Shenzhen (PRC) in 2021-2022.

Both taskbooks have the same architecture, which is based on the use of dynamic libraries and allows you to expand the set of tasks without recompiling the core of the taskbook. Each task group is implemented as a separate dynamic library with a standard set of functions that are called from the kernel at various stages of the task (the main stages are the initialization stage, which generates the initial data transmitted to the curriculum, and the final verification stage, where the results obtained by the program are compared with the control data). In addition, in the dynamic library, you can define how all the information related to the task is displayed on the screen.

Such an extensible architecture makes it possible to develop tasks of various contents, including those related to the processing of files and directories (which are automatically created when the task is initialized) and multithreaded programming, which was also demonstrated in Li Shen's graduation paper. The next stage in the development of the Unix Taskbook was the adaptation of existing task groups from the Programming Taskbook for it. When performing such an adaptation, a number of problems had to be solved.

The first problem is related to the fact that all the tasks from the basic set of the Programming Taskbook (and most of the tasks from its extensions) are implemented in Delphi Pascal using the TaskMaker learning task constructor for this language, whereas the Unix Taskbook is implemented in C++ (this makes it easy to adapt it to various operating systems of the Unix family). Therefore, it was necessary to develop a mechanism that would make it possible to transfer tasks from the basic set and extensions of the Programming Taskbook to the Unix Taskbook without rewriting the code associated with task generation.

The same mechanism that underlies the architecture of the problem books themselves, namely dynamic libraries, was used as such a mechanism. The source code of training tasks developed for Delphi Pascal can be compiled in the Free Pascal Lazarus environment, which allows you to develop programs for various platforms (note that in 2021-2022 a new version of the Programming

Taskbook core was implemented in this environment for 32- and 64-bit programming environments [3]). Thus, it is enough, without rewriting the source code of the training tasks, to compile it in the Free Pascal Lazarus version for Unix to get a dynamic library available for use in the Unix Taskbook.

Additionally, it was necessary to create a variant of the Task-Maker constructor for the Unix Taskbook. In this version of the constructor, instead of sending all the necessary data to the core of the Programming Taskbook, they are saved in a file of a certain format. In the future, this file is used by other components of the Unix Taskbook.

All other components that ensure the adaptation of tasks from the Programming Taskbook are implemented in C++ and take into account the features of the Unix Taskbook. First of all, it is a set of dynamic libraries, each of which is associated with a specific group of tasks and implements the interface used in the Unix Taskbook. As noted earlier, the functions included in this interface ensure the preparation of initial data, checking the correctness of the results and displaying the final information on the screen.

After receiving information about the task being performed, the dynamic library accesses the "basic" library prepared using the TaskMaker constructor, and with its help generates a file with complete information about the task, including the formulation, a set of source and control data, as well as additional parameters (related, in particular, to formatting data during their output on the screen). The source data is stored in the student's working directory in files of a special format, all other data is stored in memory and deleted from disk. At the next stage, the Unix Taskbook compiles and runs the training program, and after it is completed, it calls the functions of the dynamic library to verify the results and display them on the screen. All these steps are performed several times to test the curriculum on different sets of source data.

In addition to a set of dynamic libraries with tasks, an additional module was also developed that can be connected to the curriculum and allows you to enter the initial data prepared by the taskmaster into it and transfer the results to him for verification. The developed module contains a set of input, output and debugging functions that match the one used in the electronic Programming Task-book for C/C++ languages. A feature of this module that distinguishes it from similar modules of the Programming Taskbook is that the training program can be run both under the control of the Unix Taskbook and independently of it, in the mode of a regular console application. In the first case, the program receives the data prepared by the taskbook, and its results are automatically checked. In the second case, the initial data must be entered from the keyboard, the results are displayed in the console window, and the student must check their correctness on his own.

The described scheme was also used to adapt parallel programming tasks based on MPI 2.0 technology included in the Programming Taskbook for MPI-2 to the Unix Taskbook [4]. In this case, at the initial stage, the dynamic library prepares the source data for each of the parallel application processes, after

which the Unix Taskbook runs the training program in parallel mode, and after completing its work, analyzes the results obtained in each process.

LITERATURE

1. Абрамян М. Э., Ли Шэньюй. Электронный задачник по курсу «Операционные системы» / Современные информационные технологии: тенденции и перспективы развития. Материалы XXIX научной конференции. Ростов н/Д, Таганрог: Изд-во ЮФУ, 2022. С. 22–24.
2. Абрамян М. Э. Об архитектуре универсального электронного задачника по программированию // Информатизация образования и науки. 2015. № 3 (27). С. 134–150.
3. Абрамян М. Э., Козак М. В. Электронный задачник Programming Taskbook: реализация 64-разрядной версии и адаптация к новым средам программирования / Современные информационные технологии: тенденции и перспективы развития. Материалы XXVIII научной конференции. Ростов н/Д, Таганрог: Изд-во ЮФУ, 2021. С. 23–25.
4. Абрамян М. Э. Электронный задачник по параллельному программированию на базе интерфейса MPI стандарта 2.0 // Современные информационные технологии и ИТ-образование. 2017. Том 13, № 4. С. 91–104.
5. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 198-200).
6. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
7. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
8. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. The Way of Science, 56.
9. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 945–950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
10. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 938–944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>
11. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).
12. Фазлиев, Ж.Ш.(2017).Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. Интернаука,(7-3),71-73.
13. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
14. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.
15. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO'RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA'SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>